

Consumer Perceptions of Digital Marketing Strategies in the Health Insurance Sector''

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Abstract

Healthcare is not government responsibility across the world. In developing countries, like India, government healthcare schemes will not cover everyone, and people depend on private health insurance. This results in vast competition in the health insurance sector to grab a chunk of market share. Being effective in other sectors, increased number of health insurers are adopting digital marketing strategies along with traditional marketing tools. This study aims at finding the attitude of customers towards such digital marketing strategies adopted by health insurers. The sample data analysis has suggested which demographic variables should have higher order of importance while building marketing plans and strategies. Further, based on the analysis of responses, the study suggested the most effective strategic approach to approaching consumers. The authors suggested various innovative digital marketing strategies based on the analysis in line with the practice specifically for health insurance companies.

Keywords: Attitude, Innovative Digital Marketing Strategies, Healthcare Insurance

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Introduction

Healthcare is not a state responsibility across the world. In some parts of the world, the population is fortunate because the healthcare system is developed to support the citizens in case of need. Universal Healthcare is provided in some parts of the world, for example, in Canada and the residents will not spend out-of-pocket in case of any medical emergency. Even in developing countries like India, the government claims to provide universal health care and is propagated as the world's largest health program. But economists criticized the Indian prime minister's healthcare policy '*Ayushman Bharat*' also known as *Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY)* for its low budgetary allocation. According to economist Jean, it is an illusion or deception to poor Indian people as it provides only Rs 200 towards insurance per year (Drèze, 2018).

As per Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) data, India has the lowest spending on healthcare (\$186.2) as against \$10,948 per capita in the US (Data, 2021). According to Statista 2022 ("Number of lives covered under health insurance in India FY 2016-2021," 2022) during the fiscal year 2016, 64 percent of the Indian population's healthcare expenditure was out-of-pocket (OOP) (Keelery, 2022). In India, where there is a lack of appropriate government support for healthcare people need to rely on private health insurance, but people are not interested in buying health insurance both because there is a lack of awareness and due to financial constraints. This gives room for innovative marketing strategies to be adopted by health insurance companies both in the private and public sector. In India, there are four public and twenty private health insurance companies along with additional seven stand-alone health insurers competing for the market share, and even then, the penetration of health insurance is too low.

According to the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA), the Indian health insurance market is anticipated to show a compound annual growth rate of 29 percent during 2021-2025 owing to the expanding middle-class income population, and growing awareness about the benefits of health insurance plans (ReportLinker, 2020). Consumer behaviour is such that they are aware but not motivated to spend money on health insurance because they have a lack of trust in the health insurance companies to cover the hospitalization cost (Insurance, 2022). Thus, insurance companies doing business in India have great competition over the market share targeting the middle to the high-class income group of people. The middle class needs motivation and awareness to buy the insurance while the high class is looking for a seamless experience enjoying insurance. In 2019, private insurance providers accounted for the largest share of the Indian health insurance market resulting in competition. Better service offerings and brand positions would help insurance companies to grab their pie in the competitive market share. Insurance advertisements are now not only launched on traditional advertising media like newspapers and television but the insurance sector is spending more and more on digital platforms. People are more searching for insurance on Google especially due to COVID-19, insights from Google analytics show an 89-percent growth in searches related to insurance and related products (Mishra, 2020). In addition to digital platforms, as per data, there is 80 percent of the traffic on its app platforms for insurance. Insurance companies have not migrated advertising and marketing budgets from traditional to digital, they claim to have consistent expenditure with TV advertising, especially on news channels (Mishra, 2020).

Insurance providers are facing challenges to tackle with advertising (ad) on multiple platforms to ensure the reach and frequency of messages. This is giving birth to a new problem of dealing with ad clutter. The advertising avoidance rate is increasing amongst consumers. As per

research, the ad recall rate is reducing because of audiences becoming prone to avoiding the ads due to excessive clutter across different platforms, including digital (Early, 1990). Thus, there is a need for marketers to be innovative in finding better ways to break the clutter with creative and innovative strategies. Consistently writing blogs or posting on Instagram or Facebook might not be of significant help to any brand, in general, to grab the attention of the visitors and leave an ever-lasting impact. There are different new ways that research and data reflect might help the business, including the insurance sector to achieve the goal of effective and impactful advertising.

Demographic factors, income, and education, play a significant role in determining attitude of consumer and thus effectiveness of online services (Keaveney & Parthasarathy, 2001). As per research, demographic variables like age, gender, level of education, marital status, employment status, income level and area of residence influence the consumer behaviour towards online digital platforms for shopping and banking (Onyia & Tagg, 2011). In another study, demographic factors play an important role in consumer perception of value towards brand communications using social media (Klepek, 2020). Based on the research, the objective was developed to study the impact of in the demographic variables (gender, age, income, education level) on the attitude of consumers towards digital marketing adopted by health insurance companies. Further to provide better value to the insurance companies the analysis was aimed to rank which variable out of these would be the most important for marketers to consider while framing various strategies for effective marketing of health insurance products.

The study would be an addition to the existing research by ranking the demographic variables based on their impact in determining the effectiveness of consumer attitude towards digitalization of marketing content in health insurance sector.

Objectives of the Study

This paper is focused on understanding the ad clutter and how it is challenging the medical insurance brands to engage with target audiences. Further, the paper aims to suggest an innovative and creative blend of strategies to enhance consumer engagement with brands by breaking the ad clutter in the modern digital world. The paper aims to –

- To find the impact of the demographic profile of the health insurance customers on the overall attitude towards online digital marketing strategies adopted by insurance companies.
- To determine the most important and least important demographic variable for strategic usage of marketers to create an impact on consumer attitude by strategically using digitalization of insurance products.
- To measure consumer attitudes towards the various kinds of strategies adopted by health insurance companies concerning digital marketing.

Methodology

The study is based on the data collected from existing and potential consumers of health insurance. A questionnaire has been designed to collect the data from respondents. For this study, data was collected from respondents from Punjab. Data has been collected both online as well as in person from Jalandhar. With over 800 super-speciality hospitals, Jalandhar is the Asia's biggest medicare hub and that was the main reason to choose this city (Singh, 2019). For this study, the questionnaire was administered to 240 respondents and 217 questionnaires were found complete for analysis. The sample size was calculated based on the structure of the population assisted by a logical-mathematical equation. The nominal and ordinal data have been

used in the questionnaire. A five-point Likert scale has been used to measure the attitude of the respondents towards digital marketing and strategies adopted by the health insurance sector. The scoring scale of the Likert scale questions was 1=Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree and 5=Strongly Agree. For analysis of this study and to provide better recommendations to marketers for making strategies, in addition to Likert scale statements the questionnaire included demographic variables to explore gender and other categorical variables like Age, Qualifications, Occupation and Monthly Income.

Based on the literature and digital marketing practice, the popular digital marketing strategies used by companies were analysed to frame the statements and study the impact. These statements were related to general attitude towards digital marketing, email marketing strategies, social media marketing strategies, customer service and word-of-mouth strategies used by various health insurance providers. These were worded around the following:

1. Preference regarding the installation of the app on the user's device
2. Value in visiting the website of health insurance providers to seek information.
3. Convenience to purchase health insurance virtually.
4. The overall attitude towards dealing with health insurance providers online.
5. Attitude towards receiving promotional emails from medical insurance providers.
6. Value in receiving emails from health insurance providers.
7. Attitude towards promotional offers through emails in choosing insurance products.
8. Value in receiving authentic information from online sources in decision making.
9. Attitude towards engagement with social media content of health insurance providers.
10. Social media content is a valuable source of information for buying health insurance.
11. Role of customer service of health insurance providers in buying such products.

12. Preferences toward text or messenger-based customer service provided by health insurance providers.
13. Text-based customer service saves time.
14. Role of reviews posted by other customers in purchasing health insurance products.
15. Role of third-party websites endorsing health insurance (e.g., blogs or professional insurance hubs like policybazaar.com selling online comparison-based products)

Reliability and Validity of Collected Data

Reliability is the measure of the internal consistency of constructs in the study. A construct is reliable if the Alpha (α) value is greater than 0.70 (Nunnally, 1978). Construct reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha with SPSS. The results revealed that the Likert scale statements data with a five-point scale to measure the attitude toward digital marketing in health insurance with fifteen items was reliable ($\alpha = 0.949$).

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

In this study, data were collected from male and female respondents. The sample consisted of 61.29 percent male and 38.71 percent female respondents.

As per the details in the table 1, as far as the age of the respondents in sample data, 18.43 percent of the respondents were below 25 years of age, 20.28% of the respondents are in the age category 26-40 years, and 29.03 percent of respondents belong to the 41–60 years age group, and 32.26 percent respondents were above 60 years.

Table 1: Baseline demographics of Sample Respondents (n=217)

Gender	Age	Education	Occupation	Monthly_Income	Number of Records
Female	Below 25	Diploma or degree	others	20-40K	12
		Post Graduation or higher	Service/Job	20-40K	8
	Above 60	Diploma or degree	others	20-40K	4
		Others	others	Below 20K	12
		Sr Sec High School	others	Below 20K	4
	41-60	Diploma or degree	Business	Above 60K	4
		Others	others	Above 60K	4
		Post Graduation or higher	Service/Job	Above 60K	12
	26-40	Diploma or degree	others	20-40K	4
			Business	40-60K	4
		Others	Service/Job	Above 60K	4
			others	20-40K	4
			Post Graduation or higher	Service/Job	20-40K
	Male	Below 25	Diploma or degree	Student	Below 20K
Post Graduation or higher			others	20-40K	10
Above 60		Diploma or degree	others	20-40K	22
			Business	40-60K	11
		Others	others	Below 20K	6
			Post Graduation or higher	others	Below 20K
41-60		Post Graduation or higher	Service/Job	Above 60K	27
			Business	Above 60K	16
26-40		Diploma or degree	Service/Job	40-60K	10
			Post Graduation or higher	Business	20-40K
					Above 60K

The education profile of the sample consisted of 47 percent of respondents with a post-graduation degree or higher, while 37.33 percent claimed to have some diploma or degree, 1.84 percent had completed high school, and the rest of 13.82 percent belong to other categories.

Further based on the occupation, the sample consisted of 4.61 percent students, 31.80 percent in service/jobs, 20.74 percent were from doing business and the rest of 42.86 percent in other categories.

The respondents categorized based on income consisted of 19.82 percent below the monthly income of rupees twenty thousand, 33.64 percent of the respondents had a monthly income of 20-40 thousand rupees, 13.36 percent of respondents had monthly income between

40-60 thousand rupees and rest of the 33.18 percent respondents had income more than rupees sixty thousand.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

To identify if there exists a difference in attitude towards digital strategies of health insurance based on the gender of the respondents, H_0 was tested that there is no significant difference in attitude towards digital marketing strategies of health insurance companies based on the gender of the customers. To evaluate the difference between gender and attitudes, Mann-Whitney U Test was used. The test revealed that insignificant differences in attitude towards digital marketing strategies of health insurance providers of male ($Median=4, n=133$) and female ($Median=4, n=84$), $U = 930, z = -1.291, p = .197$. Hence, the null hypothesis failed to reject. There is no statistically significant difference between gender type and attitude towards digital marketing strategies of insurance companies.

The age of consumers plays a key role in determining the media consumption choice. The sample study shows that younger respondents below 25 years of age had the highest mean rank of 152.95, followed by a mean rank of 114.86 for the respondents in the age bracket of 26-40 years of age. In contrast to this, sample data suggested a higher mean rank of 158.67 in the age group 41-60 years age group. The respondents above 60 years of age had a mean rank of 35.50. To identify if there exists any significant difference in attitude towards digital strategies of marketers and age, H_0 was set that there is no significant difference in attitude towards digital marketing strategies of health insurance companies based on the age of the respondents. A Kruskal-Wallis was used for this purpose. As summarized in table 2, the Kruskal-Wallis test results showed that the age of the respondents has a significant impact on the attitudes toward digital strategies for

marketing health insurance products. The test results are, $H(3) = 171.688$, $p < .001$. Hence, this rejects the null hypothesis and there is a statistically significant difference between age and attitude towards digital marketing strategies of insurance companies.

Table 2: Importance of demographic characteristics and attitude towards digital marketing strategies.

<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>H₀</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>H Statistics</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>P value</i>
Age	Age has no impact on attitude	217	171.688	3	$P < .001$
Education	Level of Education has no impact on Attitude	217	80.427	3	$P < .001$
Occupation	Type of Occupation has no impact on Attitude	217	94.512	3	$P < .001$
Monthly Income	Monthly Income has no impact on Attitude	217	62.179	3	$P < .001$

The level of education also plays a vital role in the media consumption choices of the respondents. The sample statistics show that respondents with post-graduation or higher-level education had a mean rank of 145.25, followed by 87.41 for diploma and degree level, 24.50 by respondents at the high school completion level of education, and 55.30 as the mean rank for those in other categories. To identify if there exists any significant difference in attitude towards digital strategies of marketers and level of education; H_0 stated that there is no significant difference in attitude towards digital marketing strategies of health insurance companies based on the level of education of the respondents. A Kruskal-Wallis was used for this purpose. The Kruskal-Wallis test results showed that the level of education of the respondents has a significant impact on the attitudes toward digital strategies for marketing health insurance products. The test results are, $H(3) = 80.427$, $p < .001$. Hence, this rejects the null hypothesis and there is a statistically significant difference between the level of education and attitude towards digital marketing strategies of insurance companies.

The type of occupation was also tested to find any differences in attitude towards digital marketing strategies in the health insurance sector. Sample statistics reveal the mean rank of students (175.00), service/job (145.17), business (130.43) and for others category mean rank was (64.69). To identify if there exists any significant difference in attitude towards digital strategies of marketers and type of occupation; H_0 set was that there is no significant difference in attitude towards digital marketing strategies of health insurance companies based on the type of occupation of the respondents. A Kruskal-Wallis was used for this purpose. The Kruskal-Wallis test results showed that the type of occupation of the respondents has a significant impact on the attitudes toward digital strategies for marketing health insurance products. The test results are, $H(3) = 94.512, p < .001$. Hence, this rejects the null hypothesis and there is a statistically significant difference between the level of education and attitude towards digital marketing strategies of insurance companies.

To find out if the monthly income of respondents would make any difference in how they perceive the value of digital marketing strategies of the health insurance marketers the sample data were analyzed. It was found that respondents making above sixty thousand rupees per month had the highest mean rank of 151.52 compared to respondents in the monthly income category of rupees 40-60 thousand per month (105.84), 20-40 thousand (92.20) and respondents making below rupees 20,000 per month had a mean rank of 68.45. To identify if there exists any significant difference in attitude towards digital strategies of marketers and monthly income of respondents; H_0 was that there is no significant difference in attitude towards digital marketing strategies of health insurance companies based on the monthly income of the respondents. A Kruskal-Wallis was used for this purpose. The Kruskal-Wallis test results showed that the monthly income level of the respondents has a significant impact on the attitudes toward digital strategies for marketing

health insurance products. The test results are, $H(3) = 62.179, p < .001$. Hence, this rejects the null hypothesis and there is a statistically significant difference between the monthly income and the attitude towards digital marketing strategies of insurance companies. Health insurance marketers should make strategies to target the customers accordingly.

As suggested by the above analysis of sample statistics, Age, Occupational, Monthly income, and Education level plays a significant role in determining the attitude of the respondents towards digital marketing strategies adopted by health insurance marketers. To further analyze which demographics might play a key role Linear Modeling technique was used.

As shown in the table 3, the Age of the respondents has the highest predictor importance of 0.865 and is statistically significant as $F(3) = 166.280, P < .001$. Compared to this, the level of income holds 0.096 as predictor importance and is statistically significant at $F(3) = 35.748, P < .001$, and in the last ranking based on the predictor importance is the type of occupation with 0.026 as predictor importance and is statistically significant at $F(3) = 9.592, P < .001$.

Figure 1: Demographic Variables and Consumer Attitude

Table 3: Importance of demographic variables

Sources	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Importance
Corrected Model	166.280	12	13.857	283.522	<i>P</i> <.001	
Age	47.245	3	15.748	322.227	<i>P</i> <.001	0.865
Monthly Income	5.241	3	1.747	35.748	<i>P</i> <.001	0.096
Occupation	1.406	3	0.469	9.592	<i>P</i> <.001	0.026
Education	0.733	3	0.0244	4.997	.002	0.013
Residual	9.997	204	0.049			
Corrected Total	176.251	216				

Figure 1 shows the effect of demographic variable and consumer's attitude towards health insurance purchase. Even though Education was analysed as statistically significant but as per regression model age, income and occupation to be considered as important for determining any role in the attitude of the respondents towards digital marketing strategies of the health insurers.

Further to build marketing strategies marketers need to know which kind of content and marketing efforts would yield better value. Based on literature and practice, three kinds of Likert statements were asked, and these were statements around email marketing, customer relationship marketing and word-of-mouth strategies adopted by marketers. Spearman's rank-order correlations were run to examine the relationships between the overall attitude of the customer towards digital marketing strategies and email marketing strategies, customer relationship marketing strategies and word-of-mind strategies. There were positive and significant correlations between overall attitude and email marketing strategies, $r_s = .653$, $n = 217$, $p < .001$, overall attitude and customer relationship marketing strategies, $r_s = .829$, $n = 217$, $p < .001$, and overall attitude and word-of-mouth strategies $r_s = .732$, $n = 217$, $p < .001$. Thus, marketers should give

more importance to personalized online customer service, word-of-mouth strategies over email marketing.

Discussion

The results of the sample analysis clearly show that marketers need not to worry about gender of respondents while designing the ad content for health insurance. Further age of respondents would play the most significant role in differentiating the digital marketing strategies. Thus, marketers need to be sensitive for age as it would help them to effectively utilize each dollar spent on digital advertising or other digital marketing strategies. Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram have their native audiences and that should be kept in mind while engaging with audience. These strategies are discussed in detail in the recommendations section of the paper. Other two variables, income and education are significantly important but not that much important as the age of the respondents or prospective consumer.

Further, the type of the content that should be prioritize would include personalised customer service experience using online tools and strategically engaging with consumer to enhance their experience and thus resulting in conversion. Further, word-of-mouth plays a key role and digital marketing strategies around this have also been suggested in recommendations section. Email marketing is significant but does not as much as the customer experience and word-of-mouth would work for marketers.

Strategies Recommendations

Digital marketing can be strategically used to engage with the target audience and bring the expected results. Based on the findings of the study, age, income and occupation are most

important factor playing role in consumer response towards digital marketing strategies of a business.

Word-of-Mouth Marketing Strategies

Word-of-mouth (WOM) works better than advertisements because there is more trust in the fellow consumer's post than from a company that is just because everyone knows it is not sponsored but rather a genuine posting about the experience using the product (Keller & Fay, 2012). It works just like reviews on the internet. But it is a double-edged sword, on the one hand, positive WOM will be great, but in the case of an unhappy consumer posting his experiences on social media might be damaging for the brand. The negative WOM works even faster than positive WOM and it would need the marketing intelligence of the marketing team to nip it in the bud before it spread like wildfire (Smith & Vogt, 1995). Thus, insurance companies can create an effective digital marketing strategy with a mix of various digital platforms to nail effective marketing communication. To spread positive brand vibes businesses should post helpful content about how to keep good health, workout tips, and diet tips. Further, there could be some infographics posts from these blog pieces to be shared on social media owned by the company to bring traffic to these blogs and generate a higher search engine rating for the brand name. The pages need to be optimized for the appropriate search terms used by consumers.

Social Media Marketing Strategies

Social media is a critical tool to raise awareness about what's new, evolving, and annual health concerns and the benefits of purchasing health insurance to cover the risk of any out-of-pocket expenses. There are several ways to use social media in healthcare, including promoting awareness and sharing accurate health messaging (Newberry, 2021b). Healthcare organizations

have a responsibility to be part of the general health discussions on social media by engaging and providing credible information (Yoder, 2022). Winning the trust of the insured by raising awareness is important and it can be achieved by engaging with followers on social media with reminders about common health practices, as done in this example via Tweet from health Canada and PHAC (GovCanHealth, 2021). Another benefit of using social media in the health sector is to combat misinformation. Everyone knows the power of social media to quickly spread information to a diverse group of people. Sometimes information comes in the form of untrue statements. Thus, simply citing published credible health sources like WHO could help to stop the spread of misinformation and bring awareness to the public. The reference given here is an example showing such an effort to combat misinformation using the power of Twitter (PeterHotez, 2021). So, insurance companies can post credible information and help to stop the spread of misinformation that might be a risk to the health of the insured and the public. Similarly, during a crisis like we had during COVID-19 social media platforms can be of immense help to facilitate crisis communication. For example, the government of British Columbia hosted press conferences during the pandemic and these press conferences were streamed on Facebook Live videos along with other news channels (BCProvincialGovernment, 2021).

Instagram Marketing Strategies

Social Media platforms can be used to implement other wonderful strategies like facilitating Instagram contests to engage the audience. The insights data show that engagement increases manifold with contests letting people a chance to win something thus enhancing the interactions and engagements with the content and helping to break the clutter. Here is an example of letting visitors win a \$250 gas card from Armour Insurance when gas prices are rocketing high due to inflation (Insurance, 2021). Currently, the average of 70 percent of users on Instagram is in

their thirties, while on Facebook this age is sixty-five. But with time as the population grows old, the lines between Snapchat, TikTok and Instagram will continue to blur. Even though there are a lot of active target audiences on social media, keeping them engaged with the brand would be a challenge and that will need some creative strategies to achieve marketing communication goals.

Influencers Marketing Strategies

Further, the power of influencers on social media is always an effective strategy. Insurance companies can strategically choose the right set of influencers who can engage and encourage their followers to buy medical insurance from that brand. Influencer marketing is a terrific way for insurance providers to increase their exposure and boost engagement and follow-ups for conversion. Even though it sounds weird to see medical insurance products being promoted using Instagram influencers, it certainly is working. A Canadian company, Sonnet Insurance – focused on home and auto insurance, uses Social Media channels. Sonnet relates to its target audience on Instagram by sharing experiences in partnership with the Toronto Blue Jays and the World Cup of Hockey. Sonnet actively collaborated with local Instagram influencers as well (Fiorella, 2018). The company also had direct driving lessons on YouTube to engage with target consumers. Similarly, in the field of medical insurance businesses can implement such strategies as it will enhance the engagement with the final consumer. For example, Oscar insurance uses niche micro-influencers that appeal to digitally savvy Millennials (Fiorella, 2018). In addition to this, Oscar insurance would use various digital strategies like maintaining a blog to provide tips to the visitors on improving their health (Blog, 2022).

Strategies for Video Content

Medical insurance companies can help the public by posting content that motivates and

guides them to lead healthy lives. This can further be linked to the insurance company consistently posting on its blog to engage with the target consumer or creating video content. Video content is considered more engaging than text, so insurance companies could create short Instagram or Facebook story videos or Instagram reels and even long videos. Eighty-one percent of marketers advocate the use of video content as it has a direct and positive impact on sales, 94 percent agree that video helps to increase product awareness and understanding, and a majority of 62 percent of marketers consider video content as having top engagement metrics (Hayes, 2022). Instagram TV (IGTV) is new, but it is gaining traction among brands, so medical insurance companies can certainly make longer videos engaging consumers to spread awareness as to why they should buy the insurance. This is important, especially when the penetration of medical insurance is low as it is seen as an expenditure rather than a risk aversion strategy. Such videos can help consumers to understand the benefits of buying insurance and motivate them to do so. Digital marketing strategies suggested here are practised on various clients, including but not limited to the service sector, businesses, and the insurance sector. As per data, it is suggested that businesses must use the video for Facebook News Feed to attain higher engagement rates. Videos result in up to 25 percent more views compared to still News Feed, and it is impactful and memorable compared to still image posts. As per research viewers retain 95 percent of a message when they view it in a video compared to merely ten percent when they read it in the text (insivia, 2017). Another motivator to go for using video content by marketers is that people do not have time to read, 50 percent of executives would rather watch a video than read the text. According to Forrester Research's Dr. James McQuivey, one minute of video content equates to 1.8 million words (Arruda, 2016). Thus, it is helpful to break the ad clutter to some extent.

Conclusion

In a world flooded with overwhelming healthcare insurance ads to give everyone a headache, every marketer wants to surpass this marketing noise to get and keep the attention of consumers. There is no magic formula but a simple strategy that seems to be powerful enough to crack this clutter and surpass the advertising noise; and that is, Healthcare insurance brands can use data and technology in their favour to predict the needs and desires of prospective customers and give them the best experience possible by delivering the next-gen engagement. This refers to the use of predictive analytics and machine learning to recommend, in real-time, actions that are likely to better engage consumers based on their profile and previous actions and needs.

The Healthcare and insurance industry can offer better customer service by using personalized marketing. Personalized marketing simply put is understanding the customer needs and providing the services that are custom designed based on the needs of the consumer. According to a Salesforce survey, 66 percent of people now expect brands to understand their needs and serve accordingly (Neuner, 2021). To better understand the consumer needs, insurance companies need to invest in customer database management tools, and marketing insights to better predict the consumer needs and provide them with real-time solutions accordingly. This will ensure that

insurance providers like other brands will not waste the precious advertising dollars by overwhelming the customers with advertising or marketing, but, rather, serve them with the messages that are likely to satisfy their information needs or desires and better engage with them.

Thus, to provide the right and valued information at the right time, the insurance providers need to invest in building sound data foundations by creating a customer-data platform to provide a 360-degree customer view, deploy advanced analytics and machine learning to create customer cues and real-time triggers (Neuner, 2021). Sound data-driven marketing is the future of effectively

targeting consumers and it will benefit insurance brands to eliminate wastage of time and marketing budget thus even reducing the cost of such healthcare and insurance to the consumer.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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